

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

LABOR TRAINING AND EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN ESSENCE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

Sevil Farrukh Ibrahimova

Sheki Branch of the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Honored Teacher, Senior Lecturer

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8944-3611>

Abstract

One of the main tasks of labor education is to form the right attitude to labor in children. One of the main features of the effective organization of labor is its implementation in accordance with age and individual characteristics. The article emphasizes that the curriculum reform in Azerbaijan is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of education in the XXI century, to cultivate a creative, self-developing personality, and draws attention to the new, personality-oriented and developmental training, which is more widely applied in the practice of preschool education, and the interest shown by the child in the life and work of the elderly, as the main condition for the psychological preparation of the child for labor.

The article presents education that serves the comprehensive, harmonious development of preschool children, and how the study of Technology serves the development of preschool children's technological thinking, the formation of technological skills in them, and the acquisition of the necessary knowledge to continue their education in later stages.

Keywords: Technology, equipment, resources, technical progress, hard work, economic and social, preschool pedagogy, professions, labor process.

Relevance of the research topic. Preparing the young generation growing up in modern conditions for a free life and certain labor relations requires great competence. Every young person who is brought up in the spirit of free creativity and self-confidence, who is able to take on the responsibility of making decisions and drawing conclusions, can play a unique role in the socio-economic development of society tomorrow. The analysis of the materials I have collected gives reason to say that familiarity with the fields of labor; familiarity with labor tools; familiarity with professions; respect for working people, as well as the implementation of labor organization in various directions requires great effort from the educator, along with knowledge and skills.

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials.

"Technology" is an integrative field of education, a human activity that synthesizes knowledge from other subjects and shows its application in various fields. The study of the new integrative field of education, "Technology", and the presence of an appropriate material and technical base, allows children to acquire general labor and partial special knowledge and skills, ensuring their intellectual, physical, ethical and aesthetic development. One of the most important tasks of preparing children for school education is to educate them in readiness for labor.

The current stage of development of science and technology and the new discoveries made in this field make it an important task to raise comprehensively developed young people. [1; 32] In our republic, which is building an independent and legal state, and considers the development of free enterprise, market economy, and private ownership as its highest goal, the labor education, vocational orientation, and development of aesthetic tastes of children and

adolescents are of particular importance. In this regard, technology has a unique place and role among the educational subjects that serve the comprehensive and harmonious development of preschool children. Thus, technology should awaken in children from the first stages of preschool education a sense of love and respect for labor and working people, and should cultivate in them the ability to participate in socially useful productive work within their capabilities.

In the modern era, when technical progress is gaining momentum, the role of electronic and information technologies is increasing, and competition in a market economy is intensifying day by day, this subject serves to develop the technological thinking of preschool children, form technological skills in them, and acquire the necessary knowledge to continue their education in later stages.

At a time when the need to direct resources and information to serve the interests and benefits of people is put forward as a necessary requirement, it is becoming an important task for preschool children to acquire technological knowledge and skills and to be able to use them purposefully in their activities. The teaching of "Technology" as a subject in preschool institutions primarily stems from this necessity and is of great importance in terms of instilling life skills in preschool children. It carries. Teaching the subject "Technology", that is, Labor, in preschool institutions creates comprehensive conditions for the formation of creative abilities in children, for their continuation of education in technical fields. In the process of training, children determine the possibilities of technical activity, put forward "ideas" for solving problems, perform simple technological work and get the opportunity to evaluate the results. Teaching this subject also creates the basis for the formation of

children's character, their moral, intellectual and aesthetic development. [4; 61]

Labor is the basis of human life. The foundation of happiness is built through labor. The first condition for good upbringing is that the child understands that all the material blessings he uses do not fall from the sky ready-made and can feel that they are the fruit of someone's labor.

It is essential to start developing industriousness in children who have just entered life, who are very interested in the world around them and things, and who are eager to learn everything, from preschool age. In this regard, children are involved in labor work that is appropriate to their abilities from preschool age. The scope of their labor activity is gradually expanded and complicated. Labor forms in children, along with industriousness, such moral qualities as endurance, courage, companionship, friendship, caring, kindness, zeal, and patriotism.

Properly organized and purposefully implemented labor has a positive impact on all of a child's personal qualities and plays a decisive role in determining their future life path.

The Russian educator K.D.Ushinsky noted that real and free labor is of such great importance in a person's life that without it he loses all his value and dignity. Labor is not only a necessary condition for the development of a person, but also necessary for maintaining the degree of dignity he deserves. Therefore, the labor education of preschool children should be properly structured. This leads to the gradual formation of their ability to perform physical labor. In the process of physical labor, they receive extensive knowledge about the properties of objects, plants, animals and birds they care for, which gradually forms individual and mental characteristics in children.

It is important to start developing industriousness from a young age. Because the success of educating this quality depends largely on this period. On the other hand, in children who have just entered life, who are very interested in the world around them and things, and who are eager to learn everything, it is necessary to start developing industriousness from this period. If work is not done with children from this age towards developing industriousness, they may develop laziness or an indifferent attitude towards work. Once these qualities become a sign of character, it is very difficult to eliminate them.

The work of preschool children has its own characteristics. Their work is often related to play. This manifests itself in various forms. For example, in the game "Car Inspector", children serve passengers in the role of an inspector. In the game "Chef", the chef tries to cook a delicious dish. In the younger group of children, they feel the need to do physical work in the process of playing. [3; 48]

Combining work with play encourages children to act in a certain role (large group) and wear professional insignia (wearing a sailor's hat, carrying traffic signs, a flag, a flashlight, etc.). In the labor process, children sometimes set goals, plan work in advance, organize their activities accordingly, and work until they achieve a certain result.

Children acquire many skills and habits that are vital in their daily work activities, and they acquire the ability to work independently. In the process of work, children study the objects around them, observe the growth and development of plants. They take care of animals, get acquainted with their lifestyle. Children compare and contrast all this and try to find answers to many questions. As a result, their interest in studying these patterns gradually increases.

Preschool pedagogy sets certain goals for child labor: to acquaint children with the labor of adults, to instill in children respect for their labor, to form simple labor skills and habits, to form an interest in labor, to teach that labor has a social nature. Although it is primitive for a one and a half to two-year-old child to put on and take off his clothes, shoes, and comb his hair, its importance is quite great. By performing these actions, the child achieves the labor goal set before him. At the age of three or four, he joins in more complex household chores. Often, child labor is carried out in the form of a game. Attempting to do something has a positive effect on the development of activity, independence, purposefulness, initiative, physical strength, and mental tension in the child's character.

One of the tasks carried out during labor education is the psychological preparation of the younger generation for labor. What does psychological preparation of the younger generation for labor mean?

To make the educated understand the importance of labor in economic and social life, to explain to them the role of labor in the normal development of the human body, the formation of moral qualities and psychological processes, as well as to instill in them a love for labor and a sense of respect for working people, and a sense of hatred for those who despise labor, means psychologically preparing them for labor.

The practical preparation of the younger generation for labor is also the task of labor education. What is its essence? It consists in instilling ordinary labor skills and habits in children, adolescents and young people in the areas of self-service, household, and socially useful activities in the family, kindergarten, and school. The work carried out in this direction serves to prepare the younger generation for labor in a practical way.

In the conversation about preparation for work, one cannot forget about another type of work, mental labor. Because mental labor also has its own specific skills and habits. For example; writing poetry, drawing, composing music, scientific research, preparing for lessons, organizing and conducting lessons, etc. activities belong to mental labor. There are a number of skills and habits that characterize each of them. Instilling such skills and habits in the younger generation is also an integral part of practical preparation for work. [2; 41]

Instilling work culture, skills and habits in children is one of the tasks of labor education. When we say work culture, we mean arranging the workplace, bringing the necessary items, devices, tools, equipment, etc. for work, tidying the workplace after work, and taking safety measures.

Children are given relevant information about the measures we have listed, and are also armed with those skills and habits. The foundation of labor education is laid in the family. In the family, the various types of work of parents serve as an example for children: they strive to do the same work as their parents. Experienced parents involve their children in household and self-service work from an early age, which they are capable of.

Labor education continues in kindergarten. Children here enthusiastically participate in games depicting professions such as teaching, medicine, driving, and others.

Thus, it can be said that the development of a child's personality is formed in the process of activity. From this point of view, conveying to children what the role of labor in society is, as well as instilling in them a sense of hard work, explaining to them how necessary labor is for survival, is one of the important tasks today. The organization of children's labor activities in preschool institutions depends largely on the planning and correct understanding of work. H. Zardabi, who once highly appreciated the correct planning of labor, wrote: "It is possible to educate morally corrupt people, even criminals, with properly organized and consciously directed labor."

The child must see the connection between what, how, and why it is being done. When planning the child's work, the educator must take into account the relevance of the existing difficulties to the child's life experience and determine in advance ways to overcome them.

Work planning is related to the sequential execution of the work to be done. Tasks such as what to do first, what to do later, and why not do it differently generally require a systematic approach to work. For example, when children clearly understand the sequence of washing their hands and face, such as first rolling up the sleeves of their clothes, then washing their hands, and finally washing their face, they perform the work more efficiently. Thus, the educator determines the sequence of work, and the children follow this sequence in the process of activity.

The more purposeful and clear the children's labor activity, the more interesting and neat its implementation will be. By directing the children's actions in a logical sequence, the educator achieves more effective work with less effort and time.[8; 52]

Children in the older group often prepare the plan of the assigned work themselves. The main goal of the educator is to teach the child what he cannot do. Of course, in order for the child to plan his own activities, it is necessary to give him an example, use previous planning, and accustom him to think about his own activities in advance.

The purpose of Labor Lessons in the preschool education curriculum is to prepare children for independent life, promising professions, to acquire general skills and habits, and to adapt to various conditions based on creative thinking and active activity. Preschool children's acquaintance with different professions and gaining a certain idea encourages them to engage in direct labor. It is true that

during preschool age, a child's labor activity is mainly episodic, random in nature, and cannot be considered organized, regular, planned labor aimed directly at the production of material goods. Moreover, their acquaintance with certain labor activities and labor tools occurs mainly in the process of play, and sometimes their performance of any labor tasks bears the stamp of game activity, in other words, has a game character. In the lesson models prepared on the basis of the content standards of Technology in the areas of development, the development of children's cognitive, informative-communicative, psychomotor activities, as well as the acquisition of necessary habits, is in the center of attention. The lesson is the product of the creativity of each teacher. Therefore, it is up to the teacher to enrich and make labor activities more interesting by taking a creative approach.

Children take the labor tasks they undertake in the process of play relatively seriously, and make considerable volitional efforts to complete a certain task. If a child plays the role of a watchman, he does not leave his place for a certain period of time in connection with this task, trying to fulfill the norms required of him. In such games, children develop endurance, volitional effort, accuracy, etc. necessary for labor activity. It should be taken into account that since labor activity is always aimed at obtaining a certain result, material and moral product, creative elements always play an important role here. True, in the labor process, a completely new, original product is not always obtained, in many types of labor, a product is obtained that mainly corresponds to a certain sample or standard.

But what serves as such an example for a child in the process of play, what should he liken his product to? This example is mainly the actions and behavior of adults, as well as labor activity. Children also strive to ensure that their actions and behavior, the performance of labor tasks, closely correspond to this example. However, they do not always act as imitators. They also strive to "create", "discover". Moreover, such "discoveries" are not uncommon in their lives. However, it should be noted that children's creations are "discoveries" of what has already been created, and their "discoveries" are "discoveries" of what has already been discovered. In other words, they themselves try to determine these or other issues for themselves, independently, "without taking an example" and "without imitating", and they tend to be creative. Such creativity is most noticeable in their games related to assembly. True, in order to make this or that new object, they do not first prepare it in their heads, in an ideal form, as adults do, and then try to translate their ideas into material form. This is not relevant to their age level. However, they make this "discovery" in a visual-practical process. Sometimes, while assembling an object in the process of the game, the child himself can get a completely new object without expecting it. So, in the process of the game, the child understands the world around him, and also masters various fields of labor, labor tools and the rules for using them.

There is a special tendency for children to work in preschool age. However, it should be taken into account that in kindergarten children, work is more attractive to them because it resembles a game, in other words, it is carried out as a game. In other words, preschool children give a playful spirit even to serious work tasks assigned to them, it is this spirit that attracts them more. Thus, even children's household work is performed because it attracts them, on the contrary, the motive for doing this or that work for others is still very weak in them. However, it is precisely in the process of such work that qualities such as organization, independence, perseverance and a sense of responsibility begin to form in children, which is useful for future work. As a result, older preschool children, when on duty, are able to perform the tasks assigned to them without any reminders. They are able to organize their work in an organized manner.[5; 12]

One aspect that cannot be overlooked is that preschool children strive to do work that attracts and interests them. It is very difficult to attract preschool children to do work that does not attract or interest the child. For this, it is important to set interesting tasks for them. The research of the Soviet psychologist Elkonin attracts attention in this regard. For example, preschool children are given a piece of wood, a hammer, nails, etc., and are given the task of "making something". 72% of children give up work and do not make anything. However, as soon as they receive the task of making a small table from them, the children's attitude changes and they begin to work enthusiastically.

One of the factors that plays an important role in labor education in kindergarten children is the proper guidance of children's labor by adults. This work goes in two directions. On the one hand, adults organize interesting conversations about various types of labor, instilling interest and enthusiasm in them for labor. On the other hand, children are taught the rules for using tools and materials. It should also be noted that measures to encourage children in the work process have a very serious impact, and special attention should be paid to this aspect. It is also important to consider that a need develops when different means are used to satisfy it. When the same thing is repeated many times, a person's attitude towards it changes, and indifference towards it may arise. Therefore, it would not be right to direct a child to engage in the same thing - a labor task - for a long time, and in this case to use the same means.

As the child achieves success in that activity process, he becomes more inclined towards it. In other words, as the activity and abilities develop, the inclination also develops. This clearly shows that the development of children's abilities directly depends on the strengthening of their inclination in this or that field of activity. [9; 21]

It is of great importance for children to have spatial imagination in order to be creative in the work process.

The wider the children's spatial imagination, the more diverse their creative possibilities and the wider their field of vision. If imagination is superficial and limited, it will have a negative impact on creativity, regardless of the level of development of abilities.

Thus, it can be said that one of the main tasks facing technology classes is to develop the technical thinking and creative activity of preschool children, which can be further realized in the process of technology classes.

Result.In general, it can be said that Technology-Labor classes reflect all activities aimed at achieving general learning outcomes by determining the main goals of teaching this subject in preschool educational institutions and are focused on the capabilities and needs of each child. Labor, as the main type of activity of children, plays a key role in the comprehensive development of children. Currently, the theoretical problems of labor training include the optimal selection of its content, the improvement of labor training systems, methods for developing children's technical and technological thinking, and the effective formation of simple labor skills and habits.

At the same time, teaching this subject creates the foundation for the formation of children's character, their spiritual, intellectual, and aesthetic development, and their adaptation to socio-economic conditions by acquiring technological skills appropriate to the era.

References

1. A. Hasanov Preschool pedagogy. Baku 2000
2. Preschool education program (curriculum) in the Republic of Azerbaijan (3-6 years old) Baku-2015.
3. Javadov I.A; Jafarova L.K. Features of the new content of preschool education. Baku-2015
4. I. Hasanov, A. Rustamova.—The first manual based on the new program: "Curriculum"
5. Sh.O.Agayev S.S.Rzayeva Preschool curriculum: theory and practice. Baku 2017.
6. Methodology for organizing work in school preparatory groups (UNICEF) 2021
7. "State Standard and Program of Preschool Education." July 16, 2010.
8. Scientific and methodological journal of preschool and primary education. 2019.
9. Sh.O.Agayev S.S.Rzayeva Preschool curriculum: theory and practice. Baku 2017
10. M. Hasanov Organization of play and labor activities of preschool children. Baku 2001
11. Z.H.Orucov, Y.T.Rzayeva Technology (labor training). Baku 2006
12. Gasimova. "Labor is an important means of educating a person." Azerbaijan School 2014/5